

**AN EXAMINATION OF THE SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES IN
THE EXPRESSION OF MODERNIST IDEALS IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN
LITERATURE**

Kurbanbaeva Kamila,

The department of English language and literature

Alimova Juldiz,

2nd Year student of the faculty of foreign languages

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Abstract: *This study provides the overall analysis of English and Russian Modernism in literature. This article deals with how the so-called movement emerged and can be of use to those who seek information on the Similarities and Differences found in both literatures. Furthermore, basic elements of modernism and the key representatives are included.*

Key words: *modernism, stream-of-consciousness, Fragmentation, Ambiguity and Complexity, Symbolism, Acmeism*

Modernism plays a vital role on the enriching both English and Russian literatures that focuses on new presumptions of writers and poets of that time. Word “Modernism” means a contemporary ways of writing, living that leads to termination of realism from utilization. According to The Merriam-Webster dictionary, Modernism is defined as a practical characteristic of modern times and an attempt to find original means of expressing oneself. Similarly, in Adam Jason’s (2023) words “Modernism was a movement not just in literature but also in arts, philosophy, and cinema”. Modernism features its unique style of writing which are “stream-of-consciousness”, “Fragmentation” and “Ambiguity and Complexity” in English literature, while most Russian modernist authors attempted to illustrate their ideas with symbols. According to Tsindidis and Maslova (2016), there are two directions of Modernism movement in Russian literature, which are – **Symbolism** (considering issues of life and death, chaos and space, good and evil, beauty and ugliness, his followers introduced national and social originality into their works) and **Acmeism** (arose as a reaction to the crisis of symbolism, the Ideals of which no longer corresponded to the demands of the time. The desire for mythical experiences, the search for the innermost secrets of the soul became a thing of the past).

Using modernism elements in both literatures commenced from the late 19th century until early 20th century, allowing for assert the so-called periods’ issues.

Essential literary figures that have significant impact on the advancement of modernism in English literature are about to be discussed in the following.

In **T.S.Eliot's** poem "The Waste Land" explores life circumstances after World War First. **James Joyce's** notable contribution to Modernism that is his using of technique "stream-of-consciousness" and his work "Ulysses" is a groundbreaking narrative highlighted the challenges of the human mind. **Virginia Woolf** was a prominent figure of the target movement with novel "Mrs Dalloway" that explores complexities of modern society, experiencing structure of "stream-of-consciousness", Nour Imad Zaki informed that "Stream-of-consciousness" is one of the main structures narrative styles which explores themes of sustainable stream of considerations, emotional states and experiences in human mind. **Knut Hamsun** provided to Modernism with his use of themes relating to the Modernism elements. His works "Hunger", "Mysteries" and "Pan" emphasizes to disadvantages of modern metropolis, alienation and confusion of human nature. **Hilda Doolittle** has a significant importance on the development of modernism movement with her poems and novels that delves the themes of Modernism. **Dylan Thomas** as a modernist poet and writer surveyed notions and structures in his works. His utilization of words and imaginations of its original, rhythmic and resourceful ways. **D.H. Lawrence** explored morality and darker aspects of human being. **Paul Laurence Dunbar** as a modernist poet examined new features of literature and rejected to use of traditional conventions. **Ezra Pound** is a key figure of Modernism with his style of poetry "imagism". **Katherine Mansfield** as a modernist writer has a profound influence, with the writing forms of the short story. Her works, especially, explores themes of psychological depth, loss and love. Her mastery shown on the works "The Garden Party" and "The Doll's House". **George Orwell** was a prominent figure of the modernism movement with his novel "1984" that includes predictions of future, **Aldous Huxley** was a modernist and his famous work was "Brave New World" is about dehumanizing the world in the future.

A number of key figures have significant influence in Russian literature whose innovative works challenged traditional literary conventions and paved the complexities of the modern world.

There are some notable representatives of modernism in Russian literature. **Alexander Blok** was one of the leaders of symbolism and well-known with his emotional and philosophical poems such as "The Twelve". **Vladimir Mayakovsky** was famous for his significant contribution to poetry and drama, expressing his new opinions about life and innovation in the poem "A Cloud in Trousers". **Anna**

Akhmatova was a Symbolist poet whose works, such as “Requiem”, delves into human conditions -love, loss and suffering. **Osip Mandelstam** is mentioned his complex and profound poetry, such as in the poem “Pine Tree”, highlights personal and psychological state. **Mikhail Bulgakov** was the author of the novel “The Master and Margarita”, Bulgakov surveyed notions of the love, power and human fortune, combining elements of realism and fantasy. **Andrey Bely** was one of the leading Symbolists, Bely is known for his novel “Petersburg “, which reflects the conflict between the father and his adult son, confrontation of human in society’s rules. Vera Inber was a poet and novelist, Inber worked in the tradition of the modernist approach, exploring personal and social themes in her works. **Vladimir Nabokov** contributed to modernism movement with his use of words, techniques and works not only in Russian language but also he wrote in English languages, his novel “Lolita” reflects elements of modernism, especially in the use of language and style. **Daniil Khams** has a notable impact on Russian Modernism with his works, stories and plays, have pronounced elements of modernism and experimentation in literature. **Lev Gumilev**- although better known as a historian and ethnographer, his works often address questions of cultural identity and historical existence in a modernist movement. These authors played an important role in the development of Russian literature in the 20th century, reflecting a diversity of themes and experimenting with form, style and language, **Fyodor Dostoevsky**, a vital figure in Russian literature, is renowned for his psychological depth and exploration of the human condition. His novels delve into the complexities of morality, faith, and the human soul and his notable work is “Crime and Punishment” is about a young man’s moral turmoil and the consequences of his actions.

There are several key factors influencing the emergence of Modernism in English literature

- *Urbanization and Industrialization:* to enhance supporting family demands many people migrated to big cities, resulting in an increase of being isolated and exploring new cultural norms bring to spiritual emptiness. This urges a number of writers emphasize these themes as a centre of attention. As an example, T.S. Eliot’s work “The Waste Land” assists in understanding of brokenness, alienation and loss of faith.
- *Fragmentation and Subjectivity:* Compared to traditional assumptions, the ideas based on fragmented narrative structures captivated more writers interests. Furthermore, the majority of authors began to approach about internal existence of human nature rather than external actions.

- *Impact of World War I:* As a consequence of World War I, the majority of men conscripted, therefore the sustainability of family needs maintained by women and this circumstances led writers speak openly on their works .Such as Wilfred Owen who was sent to war and wrote his poems like “Anthem for Doomed Youth”.

The main elements that triggered to appear modernism movement in Russian literature:

- *Social and Political Turmoil:* October and February Revolutions in 1917 impacted on Russian literature. Many writers focused on political issues that played an important role in the plot, such as Alexander Blok’s poem “Twelve “ linked to the Revolution.

- *World War First:* Social unrest and the war challenged people’s spirituality and circumstances. Writers opened themes of the loss of traditional values, disillusionment and those who participated to the war allocated own experiences on their precious works.

- *Symbolism:* this phenomenon has a significant contribution in Russian Modernism period which poets and writers utilized symbols to convey thoughts and ideas. V. Solovyov’s work “*Души Мира*” plays a vital importance on development of symbolism.

In spite of the fact that English and Russian Modernism emerged from distinct historical and cultural contexts, areas , they possess several common themes and motifs that unite them as a international movement.

Both English and Russian Modernists often expressed themes of sense of Lost of faith, disappointment, and not value the traditional institutions and beliefs. World War I violently affected to many people’s spirituality. After that, in both literatures commenced learning human psyche, dreams, desires and motifs. Furthermore, in both countries’ writers focused on fragmented narrative structures to reflect their ideas in this chaotic world.

Representatives of modernism movement created new protagonists of different characteristics from previous heroes that of morally ambiguous.

Many writers saw themselves isolated and misunderstood, struggled to find the meaning of chaotic world. As a consequence of the similarities of Russian and English literature, they experienced new literary forms and techniques that have impacted to language improvement as well.

As a example of resemblance both literatures elements, it is commonly thought that, while focusing on the works of James Joyce an English Modernist and Michael

Bulgakov was an Russian modernist, it is seen that Both of them explored themes of loneliness and social alienation in their works.

Virginia Woolf and Osip Mandelstam endeavoured to convey new notions by using forms of modernism.

Conclusion

While comparing the two modernism period in literature might be understood that the political and social issues, World War I and Innovation significantly influenced people's living, morality and destiny. This circumstances are captivated numerous writers attention in that they spoke publicly civilians difficulties on their precious works exploring deeply themes relating to internal existence of human being, personal psyche, conditions and spiritual emptiness. Researching Modernism period not only in literature but also other spheres of art can bring to acknowledge profoundly each details of the movement.

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